

Practice Abstract no. 32

Data collection technologies and tools

(Updated for 2025)

The collection and handling of accurate data is essential for the effective functioning of recommendation systems, which requires multiple methods for data extraction.

This Practice Abstract addresses data collection technologies and tools. A selection of the more recent researched features explored for data collection include:

- The use of smartwatches and activity trackers to gather physical data. A relevant case is the CarpeDiem app, which integrates data from wearable devices and user surveys to analyse physical activity, sleep patterns, and dietary habits. The app provides personalised recommendations to encourage healthier lifestyles. A pilot study carried out highlighted its effectiveness in promoting long-term behavioural changes by combining objective and subjective health data. [1]
- Personalised nutrition mobile applications, including the DiabeText, a personalised mHealth intervention designed to support medication adherence and lifestyle changes in type 2 diabetes patients in Spain. This app has shown a high degree of personalisation and is patient-centred. [2]

References

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2. Zamanillo-Campos, R., Fiol-deRoque, M. A., Serrano-Ripoll, M. J., Mira-Martínez, S., & Ricci-Cabello, I. (2023). Development and evaluation of DiabeText, a personalized mHealth intervention to support medication adherence and lifestyle change behaviour in patients with type 2 diabetes in Spain: A mixed-methods phase II pragmatic randomized controlled clinical trial. *International Journal of Medical Informatics*, 176, 105103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2023.105103>

